

Utah Jazz 2022 Rebrand: Impact on Fan Identity, Loyalty, and Purchases

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of the Utah Jazz's 2022–2023 revolutionary rebrand on fan identity, loyalty, and purchase intention. The rebrand, which introduced a new “spotlight” yellow, black, and white colorway alongside a throwback purple jersey, occurred during a period of organizational transition, including roster changes and management shifts. Using a survey distributed to 177 Utah Jazz fans, this research explores how these visual changes affected fans' emotional connection to the team, their game attendance, and their likelihood to purchase merchandise. Findings revealed a significant decrease in fan identity, loyalty, and purchase intention following the rebrand, with fans expressing a strong preference for the purple throwback jersey over the new color scheme. Results indicate that revolutionary changes in team branding, particularly when done during periods of instability, can disrupt fan engagement. This research supports the importance of evolutionary rebranding, which retains core elements of team identity, to avoid alienating the fan base. Future research should explore the role of fan involvement in the rebranding process and assess real-world sales data to better understand the financial impact of such changes on sports organizations.

Keywords: Sports branding, Fan loyalty, Fandom, Sports advertising, Utah Jazz

The Utah Jazz, a professional basketball team based in Salt Lake City, Utah, has undergone significant changes since its relocation from New Orleans in 1979 (Augustyn, 2022). Despite retaining its original name, the Jazz experienced a series of transformative shifts between 2020 and 2022, including changes in ownership (The Larry H. Miller Group, 2020), management (Zillgitt, 2021), coaching (Kostecka, 2022), and roster composition (Anderson, 2022). These alterations culminated in the 2022–2023 season, where the team traded its star players for lesser-known athletes and draft picks, leaving fans grappling with an unfamiliar team and a potential decline in fan identity (Ahn et al., 2012). During this period, the most noticeable change was the team's visual rebranding, which could negatively impact fan loyalty and purchase

intention, particularly in merchandise and ticket sales (Ahn et al., 2012).

For the 2022–2023 season, the Utah Jazz adopted a striking new colorway—“spotlight” yellow, black, and white—while also retaining a throwback purple-and-blue jersey from their successful 1996–2004 seasons with John Stockton and Karl Malone (McDonald, 2022). Although the Jazz name remained consistent, the organization's branding has fluctuated over time, often alternating between different color schemes (Coles, 2022). The most recent color changes represent a revolutionary rebrand, deviating sharply from the traditional team colors and sports branding norms (Muzellec & Lambkin, 2006; Williams et al., 2021). This brief report provides concise insights into the

impact of the Utah Jazz's revolutionary rebrand on fan identity, loyalty, and purchase intentions, emphasizing the importance of brevity in academic research (Bagley, 2023).

Literature Review

Social Identity Theory suggests that individuals derive a sense of identity from the groups to which they belong, which provides a sense of worth and value (Tajfel, 1978). This theory is structured around three processes: categorization, where individuals assess their common characteristics with a group; social identification, in which they internalize the group's attributes; and social comparison, where they compare their group with others (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). These processes help explain why individuals feel a strong attachment to groups, including sports teams, and how they form a collective identity based on shared characteristics (Coombs, 2022).

In sports, the connection between fans and their teams is an example of social identification. Fans often adopt the characteristics of the teams they support, forming part of their self-identity (Coombs & Pradhan, 2024). However, when a team undergoes changes that affect its identity, such as poor performance or a rebrand, it can lead to a disruption in fan identity (Trail et al., 2005). For the Utah Jazz, the drastic rebranding in 2022 may have affected fan loyalty by altering visual elements that fans had previously identified with, leading to potential opposition (Williams et al., 2021).

Team loyalty is critical in maintaining long-term fan engagement, particularly during periods of organizational change (Bauer et al., 2008). Poor performance, changes in management, and player turnover, such as those experienced by the Utah Jazz, can weaken fan loyalty (Pradhan & Coombs, 2024). Branding becomes crucial in these situations, as it can either reinforce or further disrupt fan loyalty. The Utah Jazz's rebrand in 2022 introduced a significant change, which can have a lasting impact on fan loyalty and overall support for the team (Ahn et al., 2012).

Attitudinal Theory provides further insight into the relationship between branding and consumer behavior, particularly purchase intention. Fans' attitudes toward a rebrand can influence their behavior, such as purchasing team merchandise (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Research shows that significant changes to a team's logo or colors can cause negative attitudes, reducing the likelihood of fans purchasing new merchandise. The Utah Jazz's rebrand, which introduced a drastic color change, may result in decreased purchase intention (Collange & Bonache, 2015).

Rebranding in sports often involves evolutionary or revolutionary changes. Evolutionary rebranding involves subtle updates, while revolutionary rebranding introduces dramatic changes, such as new logos or colors (Muzellec & Lambkin, 2006). The Utah Jazz's 2022 rebrand, which introduced a new color scheme, was revolutionary, departing from its traditional colors. This kind of rebrand can provoke a stronger negative reaction, especially when fans are not consulted or involved in the process (Williams et al., 2021).

Logos are essential in fostering fan identification and loyalty, and drastic changes to logos or colors can have significant consequences (Ahn et al., 2012). Fans often feel a deep connection to these visual elements, and any changes to them can lead to a loss of fan identity. Studies show that the more drastic the rebrand, the more likely fans will react negatively, as seen with the Utah Jazz's 2022 rebrand, which introduced new colors and designs not linked to the team's history (Ahn et al., 2012; van Grinsven & Das, 2015; Williams et al., 2021). Maintaining some continuity in branding, such as colors, can help ease fan transitions and mitigate negative reactions (Williams et al., 2021).

This research aimed to answer three questions:

RQ1: How does the rebranding of the Utah Jazz affect fan identity?

RQ2: How does the rebranding of the Utah Jazz affect fan loyalty?

RQ3: How does the rebranding of the Utah Jazz affect fan purchase intention?

Method

To address the research questions on how the Utah Jazz rebrand affected fan identity, loyalty, and purchase intention, a survey method was employed. The survey was distributed over one week during the Utah Jazz's 2022-2023 season (January 17-24, 2023) via Facebook fan groups, targeting groups like Hardcore Utah Jazz Fans, Utah Jazz Nation, and others. A total of 177 participants completed the survey, with the majority falling within the 25-54 age range (80%). The gender distribution was 59.32% male and 40.68% female, and over 81% of respondents had access to televised Utah Jazz games during the season.

The survey, created on Qualtrics, consisted of 20 questions addressing both independent and dependent variables related to the rebrand. Questions measured participants' affinity for past and current colorways, their self-identification as fans, and their purchasing

behavior. Responses were recorded using a Likert scale (1 = “do not like” to 5 = “strongly like”). Data analysis was performed using SPSS, where paired-sample t-tests were used to assess the changes in fan identity, loyalty, and purchase intention before and after the rebrand. This approach provided insight into how fans responded to the Utah Jazz’s new visual branding and its potential implications on future fan engagement and sales.

Results

A paired-samples t-test in SPSS was used to determine statistical significance in the difference between fan identification, fan loyalty, and purchase intention. Respondents were asked paired questions rating their attitudes and behavior before and after the rebrand.

Fan Identity

In determining fan identification before and after the rebrand by asking respondents how they self-identify as a Utah Jazz fan, the decrease was statistically significant from before to after the rebrand ($t=5.999$, $p<.001$) with a mean difference of .294.

Fan Loyalty

Fan loyalty was determined by asking two questions that compared previous behavior to current behavior. The first measure of fan loyalty was in identifying with the team players. Respondents indicated a statistically significant decrease in how well they felt they knew the players on the team this year ($t=7.817$, $p<.001$) with a mean difference of .605. The second measure of fan loyalty was in game attendance. There was a statistically significant decrease in game attendance this year over last year ($t=5.257$, $p<.001$) with a mean difference of .198. The decrease indicated in both questions indicated a decrease in fan loyalty.

Purchase Intention

Respondents were asked about their purchasing behavior of Utah Jazz merchandise, and when compared to last year, there was a statistically significant decrease in Utah Jazz merchandise ($t=8.674$, $p<.001$) with a mean difference of .358. Respondents who indicated they intended to purchase merchandise this season indicated the purple colorway as preferred (51.52%) to the yellow, black, and white colorway (40.91%).

Table 1

Statistical differences between paired groups

	<i>Mean Difference</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Fan Identity	.294	5.999	<.001
Fan Loyalty (Players)	.605	7.817	<.001
Fan Loyalty (Attendance)	.198	5.257	<.001
Purchase Intention	.358	8.674	<.001
Rebranding Attitude (Purple)	.086	.882	.379
Rebranding Attitude (Y,B,W)	1.7	14.77	<.001

Rebranding Attitude

When all of the past uniform colorways collectively were compared to the purple throwback uniforms being used this year, there was no significant difference. However, when past colorways were compared with the new yellow, black, and white colorway, there was a large statistically significant decrease in likeability ($t=14.77$, $p<.001$) with a mean difference of 1.7. When respondents were presented with all of the past and current colorways and asked to identify their preferred uniform, the throwback purple uniform was the favorite uniform (32.57%), followed by the orange, red, and yellow city jersey introduced the year before (26.86%). The newly rebranded yellow, black, and white colorway was indicated as the favorite colorway by 11.43% of respondents.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of the revolutionary rebrand implemented by the Utah Jazz on fan identity, loyalty, and purchase intention. The results confirmed previous research and theoretical expectations, indicating a decrease in all three areas. The first research question examined whether the rebrand diminished fan identification, with respondents reporting lower levels of self-identification as Utah Jazz fans compared to the previous year. This reduction in fan identity aligns with the expectation that significant visual changes can disrupt the emotional connection fans have with their teams.

Given the decline in fan identification, it follows that fan loyalty and engagement behaviors, such as game attendance and merchandise purchases, would also decrease. Respondents reported feeling less familiar with the players due to a significant turnover in the roster, which further weakened their connection to the team. Additionally, game attendance dropped compared to the previous season, and merchandise sales also declined. Despite the rebrand's potential to stimulate merchandise sales, fans appeared less inclined to purchase items, even with the availability of the popular purple throwback jersey.

The rebrand introduced a new yellow, black, and white color scheme, which received lower favorability compared to previous colorways. While fans favored the purple throwback jersey, the new jerseys were met with less enthusiasm. This sentiment highlights the importance of maintaining continuity in visual elements that resonate with the team's history. With significant changes occurring at multiple levels of the organization—from ownership to players—fans may have felt disconnected from

the team's identity. The rebrand, including its new visual symbols, was interpreted as a personal change, affecting not only the organization but also how fans saw themselves as part of the team.

Logos and colors are critical identifiers for fans, and any significant change can put fan identity at risk. Even minor changes, as seen in the Utah Jazz's 2012 logo update, can negatively impact fan loyalty (Ahn et al., 2012). The 2022 rebrand, with its complete colorway change, represents a revolutionary shift that likely exacerbated this effect. With so many changes in the organization, the logo change may have been one step too far, making it difficult for fans to maintain their identification with the team. Previous research suggests that loyal fans often seek to reconcile changes in team identity by focusing on the positives. However, in this case, the rebrand made it difficult for fans to feel part of the in-group. Despite a strong connection to the Utah Jazz in the previous season, fans did not feel inclined to purchase new merchandise. Even when provided with the option to buy the purple throwback jersey, the new yellow, black, and white colorway failed to resonate. As a result, the rebrand had a more profound impact on fan identity, loyalty, and purchase behavior than anticipated.

It is also worth noting that the instability of the roster may have discouraged fans from purchasing player jerseys, as they faced the risk of buying a jersey for a player who might not stay with the team long term. However, following this research, players such as Lauri Markkanen were selected for the NBA All-Star game, and rookie Walker Kessler was included in the Rising Stars game. As these players become more established, it is possible that fan identification with the new colorway and roster may improve in future seasons.

Analysis

The analysis of this study highlights the significance of fan identity in sports organizations and how it is influenced by social identity theory. Fans often associate their personal identity with their team, making any changes to the team's branding a highly sensitive issue. In the case of the Utah Jazz, the rebranding occurred during a period of transition, marked by a new roster and predicted losses. Although the Jazz began the season with a strong 10-3 record, their performance declined as the season progressed. This decline, coupled with the dramatic rebrand, had a negative effect on fan identity, as fans generally resist associating with a losing team. The introduction of the purple throwback jersey, associated with a period of past success, provided some relief,

indicating that fans gravitated toward familiar and positive associations with the team's history.

The resistance to the new yellow, black, and white colorway can be attributed to both its divergence from the team's traditional colors and the timing of the rebrand. While fans had previously embraced bold color choices, such as the city jersey from the 2021–22 season, the combination of organizational changes and the introduction of unfamiliar colors led to a disconnect. The research suggests that fans are more open to color changes when they feel a strong connection to the team's performance and identity. In contrast, during the 2022–23 season, fans were less inclined to embrace the new colorway, resulting in decreased fan identity and loyalty.

The results also confirm the attitudinal theory, which posits that negative reactions to a rebrand can lead to declines in purchase intention. This was evident as fans reported lower intentions to purchase merchandise featuring the new color scheme. The research suggests that fans may have reacted more positively to the rebrand if the Utah Jazz had solicited public input or communicated the changes more effectively. This cooperative approach could have reduced the perception that the rebrand was imposed by new ownership, thus fostering a sense of inclusion among fans.

Communication plays a vital role in how fans perceive changes within a sports organization. According to social identity theory, fans see themselves as part of an in-group, and sudden, unilateral changes by an out-group (such as new ownership) can create tension. The Utah Jazz's failure to engage fans in the rebranding process may have exacerbated feelings of disconnect. Involving fans in the decision-making process, particularly regarding logos and colors, could have helped align the rebrand with fan expectations and reduced negative reactions. By fostering cooperative communication, the team could have preserved fan loyalty and encouraged greater acceptance of the rebrand.

From a practical standpoint, this research reinforces the idea that fans are less likely to accept revolutionary rebrands, particularly those that involve significant color changes. Evolutionary rebrands, which involve minor adjustments while retaining core visual elements, are more likely to maintain fan loyalty and purchase intention. Given the Utah Jazz's situation—facing an already precarious fan identity—introducing a revolutionary rebrand may have been ill-timed. Fans are more likely to embrace changes that align with their existing associations with the team, especially during

periods of instability.

This research leads to the conclusion that the Utah Jazz's decision to introduce a spotlight yellow colorway during a transitional period proved to be unnecessary and detrimental to fan identity and loyalty. The rebrand failed to resonate with fans and led to decreased sales. A more successful strategy would have been to maintain the existing branding or introduce the spotlight yellow as a city jersey, giving fans time to adjust. Ultimately, the findings suggest that sports organizations should proceed cautiously when rebranding, especially during times of organizational change, and prioritize fan engagement to ensure loyalty is preserved.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant impact of rebranding on fan identity, loyalty, and purchase intention, particularly in the context of sports organizations like the Utah Jazz. The introduction of a revolutionary rebrand, with a spotlight yellow colorway, during a transitional period for the team proved to be detrimental to fan engagement. The mid-season timing of the survey provides a valuable snapshot of fan reactions, but it also limits the scope of the findings, as further player trades and team developments may have amplified the negative effects on fan loyalty. Future research could benefit from exploring how different demographics, such as younger fanbases, respond to rebrands and from incorporating actual sales data to measure the real-world financial impact of branding changes.

The study also suggests that successful rebrands in sports should consider evolutionary rather than revolutionary changes, particularly during periods of organizational instability. Maintaining connections to team history and involving fans in the decision-making process may help preserve fan identity and loyalty. As fan identity is critical to the revenue-generating aspects of sports teams, such as merchandise sales and game attendance, organizations must approach rebranding with caution and emphasize the importance of fan engagement to mitigate negative outcomes.

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